

VERBALIZATION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC CATEGORY "TOLERANCE" IN THE POLITICAL SPEECHES OF BARACK OBAMA

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Abstract:

The article explores the verbalization of the communicative-pragmatic category "tolerance" in the political speeches of Barack Obama. It analyzes how tolerance is expressed linguistically using inclusive pronouns, contrast, and antithesis as well as their pragmatic function. The study is conducted using discourse and pragmatic analyses showing that tolerance is used to unite people, promote cooperation, and accept differences.

Key words:

Barack Obama, tolerance, political discourse, communicative-pragmatic, inclusive pronoun, antithesis.

Introduction

Tolerance is an important moral value in multinational countries, as it shows respect, unity, and understanding between different social, cultural, and religious groups. Moreover, tolerance is used in political discourse to shape public opinion and social relations. Barack Obama is the 44th president of the United States, and also, he was the first African American president. Most of his speeches are devoted to racial discrimination, immigration, religious diversity, and so on. This study is aimed at analyzing "tolerance" as a communicative-pragmatic category in the political speeches of Barack Obama using discourse and pragmatic analysis.

According to T. van Dijk, political discourse is the speeches and texts that are used in the political context with all participants that are involved, such as politicians, citizens, and the public [Van Dijk, 1997:12–13].

The Cambridge Dictionary defines tolerance as "willingness to accept behavior and beliefs that are different from your own, although you might not agree with or approve of them" [Cambridge Dictionary, 2026]. Another dictionary, Collins English Dictionary, defines it as "the quality of allowing other people to say and do as they like, even if you do not agree or approve of it" [Collins English Dictionary, 2026]. According to Makhamadalieva, tolerance in communication is based on politeness, respect for the speaker, and avoidance of conflict [Makhamadalieva, 2021:106].

"Communicative-pragmatic" refers to the language use in the specific context of communication and focuses on the aim of communication, effect on the listeners, and what the speaker's intention is [Searle, 1969; Grice, 1975]. As a communicative-pragmatic category, tolerance is expressed by specific language choices, speech acts, evaluative expressions, and rhetorical strategies to influence the audience [Van Dijk, 1998]. From a pragmatic perspective, tolerance functions as a strategy of speech behavior realized through a set of linguistic means and aimed at maintaining communicative parity, preventing discrimination, and mitigating conflict situations in political interaction [Никитина, 2022:4].

In the speech A More Perfect Union, Barack Obama presents tolerance as unity and cooperation. The inclusive pronoun "we" is repeated to create a feeling of fellowship and shared responsibility. By saying this, "We cannot solve the challenges... unless we solve them together," he tries to invoke cooperation among people [Obama, 2008a]. From a pragmatic perspective, this encourages people to feel unity and be responsible for the common problems.

Obama also uses contrast: "different stories, but common hopes" and "may not look the same... but we all want to move in the same direction" [Obama, 2008a]. The contrast is used to emphasize that people may be different in race, background, or experience, but they share similar aims. The conjunction "but" connects difference with unity. This means tolerance is shown as accepting differences while focusing on shared hopes. Similarly, in his 2008 victory speech, he also uses the antithesis "young and old, rich and poor, Democrat and Republican, Black, White, Hispanic, Asian..." to emphasize the fact of diversity and inclusivity [Obama, 2008b]. By providing antithesis and saying "we are, and always will be, the United States of America," Obama highlights that even though people are different, they are citizens of one government who have the same rights [Obama, 2008b].

The metaphor "perfect our union" highlights the idea of improving the country together [Obama, 2008a]. It reminds the audience about national values and unity. The expression "a better future for our children and our grandchildren" creates an emotional effect, reminding us to make a better future for the upcoming generation [Obama, 2008b]. This makes the message stronger and more persuasive.

Conclusion

The analysis of the political speeches of Barack Obama shows that the communicative-pragmatic category "tolerance" is expressed through the inclusive pronoun "we," contrast, antithesis, metaphor, and future-oriented appeals. From a pragmatic perspective, these linguistic choices aim to foster unity, promote cooperation, and create a sense of shared purpose. This analysis provides the important role of language in political discourse and shaping public attitudes towards unity and respect.

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